

OPENNESS AND USABILITY OF BIG DATA OF THE PAST AND TIME MACHINE PROJECT – DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE EUROPEAN CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Cultural heritage sector in Europe consists of vast number of professional organisations, networks, infrastructures and platforms in various areas and domains, as reflection of Europe rich history and cultural diversity. In last decade they increasingly coordinate their work on building digital capacity in the cultural heritage sector by giving momentum to existing policies and developing of common practices and shared solutions, which is also supported by corresponding EU activities, such as for example, Expert Group on Digital Cultural Heritage and Europeana (DCHE).

Majority of European countries actively support digitisation and digital preservation of cultural heritage and provided access to the corresponding digitised resources, through various set of actions – ranging from policy initiatives and legislations like the Recommendation on the digitisation and online accessibility of cultural material and digital preservation (2011/711/EU) and the New European Agenda for Culture, programmes such as the European Year of Cultural Heritage 2018 or the European Framework for action of Cultural Heritage till building of the Europeana Europe's digital platform for cultural heritage which function as the European cultural hub. Majority of these activities are focused on development of digitisation technologies, digital preservation and innovative cultural projects that will make cultural heritage accessible to all and enhance its visibility.

Following these trends, in 2019 the Declaration of cooperation on advancing digitisation of cultural heritage was launched with aim to facilitate and promote joint work and better use state-of-the-art digital technologies in addressing risks that Europe's cultural heritage is facing, encompassing three pillars of action:

- a pan-European initiative for 3D digitisation of cultural heritage artefacts, monuments and sites;
- re-use of digitised cultural resources to foster citizen engagement, innovative use and spill-overs in other sectors;

- enhancing cross-sector and cross-border cooperation and capacity building in the sector of digitised cultural heritage (“EU Member States sign up to cooperate on digitising cultural heritage”).

In times of global pandemic crisis caused by COVID-19 outbreak, importance of digital access to cultural heritage is additionally emphasized. European Heritage Alliance Manifesto „Cultural Heritage: a powerful catalyst for the future of Europe“, launched in 2020 highlights seven incarnated ways in which cultural heritage can act as a catalyst for positive change, including digital transformation where Europe plays a leading role in digital cultural heritage and has the potential to forge ahead with new technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning based on humanistic and ethical principles“. It also outlines collaboration the use of digital technology and expertise, innovation, narrowing digital gap between cultural institutions, as well as critical engagement in education and knowledge sharing (European Heritage Alliance, 2020).

EU-funded Time Machine Project, an ongoing Europe-wide initiative started in 2017 with the joint goal of digitising the entire European cultural heritage, builds on these foundations with idea of forming a unique alliance between the best European players in the humanities, sciences and technologies for implanting this goals. Time Machine, the largest and most ambitious project ever created at the intersection of culture heritage and information science, is built around the vision to develop the big data of the past – a widely distributed digital information system mapping the European social, cultural and geographical evolution across times by designing and implementing advanced new digitisation and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. This large-scale digitisation and computing infrastructure, capable to map 5,000 years of European history, aims to revive historic data into (virtual) reality and convert them into a living social and economic resource that will start and influence various cultural, economic and social shifts (Time Machine Consortium, 2019a).

Time Machine plans to transform kilometres of archival fonds, abundant museum collections and various geo-historical data sets into a distributed digital information system by bringing together academic research teams, heritage institutions and industry, from major GLAM institutions to leading technology companies in the field of digitization and artificial intelligence. Such interdisciplinary operational environment is indispensable for developing the big data of the past that would launch a new era of open access to sources from history and culture field, as well as provide practical collaborative model for science and technology to actively contribute to safeguarding European identity and democratic values (Time Machine Consortium 2019b).

Time Machine is organised through four basic pillars: Science and Technology, Time Machine Operation, Exploitation Avenues and Outreach and Innovation while project infrastructure is implemented through Time Machine Organization (TMO).

The Time Machine ecosystem includes academic, research and cultural institutions, as well as large businesses and innovative small and medium-sized enterprises, government bodies and associations of the civil society involved in cultural heritage which make it the widest initiative for digitizing European cultural heritage, created at the intersection of culture heritage and information sciences. This collaborative network target specific objectives:

- addressing the scientific and technological challenges in artificial intelligence (AI), robotics and ICT for social interaction in order to develop the big data of the past, while boosting these key-enabling technologies in Europe,
- building the infrastructure for digitisation, processing and simulation that will support a sustainable management and operational model (the “TM franchises” in the form of local Time Machines), as well as create the basis for and engagement with communities (citizens, scientists, innovators) participating in the development and use of Time Machine,
- creating innovation platforms in promising application areas, by bringing together developers and users for the exploitation of scientific and technological achievements, and therefore leveraging the cultural, societal and economic impact of Time Machine,
- fostering favorable framework conditions for the outreach to all critical target groups, and for guiding and facilitating the uptake of research results produced in the course of the Time Machine initiative (Time Machine Consortium 2019b).

TMO is formally established in 2019 and operates as sustainable joint platform for future development and research in technology, science and cultural heritage and their positioning in Horizon Europe programs, as well as framework for strategic planning and lobbying activities. Today this global initiative gathers thousands member organisations, thus establishing the largest European network of academic, research and cultural institutions and the IT sector, that allows cross-sector communication and partnership structure capable to provide required global collaboration and resources for mass-scale digitization and shared computing infrastructure, as well as explore potentials related to research, innovation, technological development and cultural heritage. (see Time Machine Consortium, 2019b). TMO is headquartered in Vienna, with additional offices in Lausanne, Amsterdam and Budapest, engaged in building of network and infrastructure that implements the goals and activities of the Time Machine road maps (servers, databases, platforms, etc.), supporting local TM projects, organizing national TM days, TMO conferences, developing new services and projects, etc.

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